

the difference in NBOMD was because the neutral detergent fiber (NDF) in B degraded faster than in C. This was contributed by higher digestibility of cellulose and hemicellulose, the two components of NDF.

The difference between A and B was perhaps due to a combination of higher

neutral detergent solubles (NDS), higher crude protein (CP), and lower cell wall (NDF) contents for A. The higher NBOMD in A was attributed to the higher NDF ($r = 0.9$) and cellulose digestibility ($r = 0.7$) and CP content ($r = 0.66$). Varieties with lower NDF contained more CP.

The NBOMD of the three common varieties was similar during both years, indicating no year effect. The varieties were grown under the same agronomic conditions in the same soil, implying that the difference in NBOMD could only be because of their genetic makeup. ■

Heterosis in chemical composition and digestibility of rice straw

M. Singh and A. K. Gupta, Animal Science Department, Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology (GBPUAT), Pantnagar, 263145, Uttar Pradesh, India; and H. P. Singh, Plant Breeding Department, GBPUAT

The straw of 15 F_1 crosses and that of their 10 parents were collected from a rice breeding experiment. The chemical composition and nylon bag (72-h) dry matter digestibility (NBDMD) were determined for each (see table).

Crossing two varieties resulted in a hybrid with higher NBDMD than that of the parents, except for Narendra 118/Pant Dhan 6. Eliminating the cross with negative heterosis (Narendra 118/Pant Dhan 6) from heritability (h^2) estimation by regression gave h^2 values of 0.86 for NBDMD and 0.82 for nylon bag organic matter digestibility (NBOMD).

The crude protein (CP) content in most hybrids was greater than that of both or one of the parents. Both Narendra 118 and Pant Dhan 6 had

Chemical composition (%) and NBDMD (%) of rice straw from different parents and hybrids.

	Parents			Hybrids			
	CP	NDF	NBDMD	CP	NDF	NBDMD	NBOMD
IR58 ^a	4.2	70.1	47.1	—	—	—	—
UPR85-32	3.5	73.7	42.0	4.9	65.2	51.7	52.9 b
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	4.9	69.5	49.9	51.0 ab
IET7613	4.7	68.6	49.9	5.4	68.2	54.6	55.7 c
UPR83-169	5.1	66.2	49.0	6.5	65.8	54.5	55.6 c
UPRH39	5.6	71.3	46.9	5.4	67.3	50.2	51.4 ab
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.3	49.3	5.8	67.6	53.8	54.8 c
Narendra 118 ^a	5.1	69.2	48.0	—	—	—	—
UPR82-43	3.6	72.1	41.2	5.3	66.9	49.8	51.1 ab
UPR85-32	3.5	73.7	42.0	6.0	67.7	50.7	51.8 b
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	6.5	66.5	52.2	53.4 bc
IET7613	4.7	68.6	45.9	6.1	70.6	52.0	53.0 bc
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.3	49.3	4.7	68.1	47.9	49.0 a
IET6223 ^a	4.4	66.6	45.1	—	—	—	—
IET7566	4.6	66.4	46.3	5.3	66.7	51.2	52.3 b
IET7613	4.7	68.4	45.9	5.7	64.6	50.1	51.2 ab
UPRH39	5.6	71.3	46.9	5.4	68.5	49.7	50.9 ab
Pant Dhan 6	5.3	69.8	49.3	6.0	69.0	52.2	53.4 bc

^aIR58, Narendra 118, and IET6223 were crossed with the varieties grouped below them to produce hybrids.

relatively higher dry matter digestibility (DMD) and CP, so no further improvement could be expected in the hybrids.

Polygenes, the combination of which seem to be identical in these two varieties, may control the CP content.

The positive correlation between CP and DMD and the simultaneous reduction in the neutral detergent fiber (NDF) of hybrids are desirable for improving the nutritive value of straw. ■

Allelic relationship among fertility-restoring genes in rice

J. Ramalingam, N. Nadarajan, C. Vanniarajan, and P. Rangasamy, Agricultural Botany Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied the allelism for the restoring gene(s) present in purified testers received from IRRI. The five testers, IR24 (T_1), IR54742-22-19-3 (T_2), IR29723-143-3-2-1 (T_3), IR9761-19-1 (T_4), and ARC11353 (T_5), were tested for

Segregation pattern of pollen and spikelet fertilities in test cross F_1 progenies. Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

Test cross	Total plants observed (no.)	Pollen fertility ^a		Spikelet fertility ^b	
		Fertile	Sterile	Fertile	Sterile
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_2$)	200	169	31	169	31
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_3$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_4$)	200	175	25	174	26
V20 A ($T_1 \times T_5$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_3$)	200	165	35	167	33
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_4$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_2 \times T_5$)	200	168	32	166	34
V20 A ($T_3 \times T_4$)	200	178	22	178	22
V20 A ($T_3 \times T_5$)	200	200	—	200	—
V20 A ($T_4 \times T_5$)	200	161	39	163	37

^aPollen fertility = fertility \geq 60%, sterility = 0%. ^bSpikelet fertility = fertility \geq 80%, sterility = 0%.

their restoration and inheritance patterns during 1992-93 rabi season (Sep-Jan). All were found to be effective restorers and inherited digenically.

To determine the relationship among the genes, these five testers were crossed in all possible combinations, excluding reciprocals. The F₁ generation of 10 R × R combinations was raised along with cytoplasmic male sterile line V20 A; A × (R × R) crosses were made. These

10 test cross F₁ progenies (A × (R × R)) were raised at 20- × 19-cm spacing during 1993 kharif season (Jun-Sep). Each combination had 10 rows with 20 plants per row. Their pollen and spikelet fertilities were scored (see table).

The restorer lines differed in their gene action. The test cross progenies from T₁ × T₃, T₁ × T₅, T₃ × T₅, and T₂ × T₄ did not yield any sterile progeny. These lines have identical R alleles

between them while remaining crosses showed segregation, indicating the alleles differed among their parents. These results suggest that the five restorer lines can be divided into group 1 = T₁, T₃, and T₅ and group 2 = T₂ and T₄, which possess different pairs of R genes. A suitable combination of any two of the pairs seems to restore fertility in male sterile lines. ■

Breeding methods

Identifying restorers and maintainers for five cytoplasmic male sterile lines

F. U. Zaman, M. J. Abraham, A. R. Sadananda, F. Mohammad, and Y. Raj, Genetics Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012, India

Two new cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, Pusa 3 A and Pusa 5 A, were developed. Pusa 3 A has in its background high-yielding Basmati variety Pusa Basmati 1. Pusa 5 A has the aromatic, non-Basmati line Pusa 150. These lines, along with IR58025A, PMS2 A, and PMS3 A, which possess CMS wild abortive cytoplasm, were used to make test crosses. During the 1994 wet season, 326 hybrids and their respective parents were evaluated to identify effective restorers and maintainers for the CMS lines. Each genotype was transplanted in 3-m rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Standard agronomic practices were followed.

Five plants from each genotype were randomly selected and used for analyzing pollen and spikelet fertility. Anthers from upper, middle, and lower portions

Restorers and maintainers for five CMS lines. New Delhi, India. 1994.

CMS line	Restorers (no.)	Restorers	Maintainers (no.)	Maintainers
IR58025 A	36	PRR3, PRR5, PRR7, PRR8, PRR11, PRR12, PRR16, PRR22, PRR23, PRR25, PRR34, PRR35, PRR38, PRR42, PRR43, PRR44, PRR74, PRR79, PRR82, PRR98, PRR99, PRR100, PRR101, PRR102, PRR103, PRR104, PRR105, PRR107, PRR112, PRR113, PRR114, PRR115, PRR116, PRR117, PRR118, PRR119	7	TC7-2-1-92-39, TC11-3, TC23, TC25-41, P615-K-61, P615-K-271, P615-4-1
PMS3 A	13	PRR2, PRR8, PRR10, PRR24, PRR33, PRR45, PRR47, PRR55, PRR83, PRR84, PRR85, PRR87, PRR89	4	P615-K-160, RCPL 1-87-4, PP94-429, PP94-432
PMS2 A	4	PRR3, PRR5, PRR44, PRR85	3	ADT2008-2-7-1, P1191-3, P1192-2
Pusa 3 A	6	PRR69 ^a , PRR70 ^a , PRR71 ^a , PRR90, PRR94, PRR95	5	TC4-721, TC7-3-1, TCII-7-3-4-1, TC120, HKR91-410
Pusa 5 A	2	PRR57, PRR91	2	P615-K-61, P615-K-172
Total	61		21	

^a = Basmati restorers.

of half emerged panicles were collected and squashed in 2.2% I-KI stain to observe pollen fertility. Cultivars with up to 1% pollen and spikelet fertility were classified as perfect maintainers, those with 60-100% pollen and 80-100% spikelet fertility as potential restorers, and the rest as partial restorers.

Three potential Basmati restorers were identified for Pusa 3 A. The frequency of restorers (19%) was higher than that of maintainers (6%) (see table).

We are using the potential restorers to develop new hybrids with improved quality characteristics. Some perfect maintainers with good agronomic traits are being converted into new CMS lines. ■

Androgenesis in rice breeding

N. Mandal, Chinsurah Rice Research Centre, Hooghly 71 21 02, India; S. Sinha and S. Gupta, Botany Department, Bose Institute, Calcutta 700009, India

Plant regeneration efficiency from anther culture of F₁ cross Pankaj × *O. rufipogon* has been improved using He2 + NAA + Kin 0.5 + ABA 2 mg/liter + 5% maltose as

the callus induction medium (see table). Our objective was to transfer the submergence tolerance from the wild species *O. rufipogon* Griff. to the *O. sativa* variety Pankaj.

We used modified MS (NAA 0.5 + Kin 2 mg/liter + 3% sucrose) medium for plant regeneration. Several chlorophyll-deficient plants (albino, xantha, viridis, albo-viridis, virido-albina, virido-xantha,

and striata) and green plants that have different ploidy numbers were obtained. Among the regenerated plants, 73.3% were double haploids. These lines were grown in the field, where 74.8% survived. We examined 696 androgenic lines for different qualitative and quantitative characters. Statistical analysis revealed that the characters within one line were relatively uniform and stably heritable. Among